

Educational Findings: Social Cause via Corporate Social Responsibility

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Social Cause via Corporate Social Responsibility

Introduction

Globalization is an issue that gathered both acceptance and criticisms with time. In one perspective, the phenomenon resulted in trade of wide variety of goods and services. Similarly, globalization is a major reason for reduction in transportation costs and transfer of technology. It also addressed many social issues such as labor rights and labor laws. Nevertheless, the major adverse effect of globalization is social inequality (Lee, et.al, 2006). Social inequality refers to irregular distribution of opportunities and rewards for special social statuses in a group or community. Because of social inequality, problems like death rate, sickness, poverty and crime increases in society. Social inequality also results in high rate of unemployment. According to a survey, globalization resulted in more unemployment in contrast to job creation. However, many social issues are those that multinational companies tried to resolve with their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

Discussion

The most prominent social issue in modern time is food and nutrition. In past two decades, the global demand for food was record breaking. The demand is expected to keep on increasing along with the world's population. In 2005, the food stock drained with continuous demand and consumption. Further, in the same year the production was radically destroyed by climate catastrophe in food-producing nations. In 2007, boost in oil prices raised the cost of fertilizers resulting in expensive food production.

Further, as the international food prices unexpectedly increased beyond limits, production countries created artificial shortage of food and price shocks. Many exporting nations imposed

heavy taxes, due to which, importers were left without a choice but to purchase at higher cost to sustain local supplies. The international grain industry was more priced when speculative investments injected in open markets. In following years, the supply got stability yet the prices remained higher affecting the growth and standard of living in developing nations. According to United Nation (UN), around 854 million people were undernourished and crisis may lead additional 100 million people towards poverty and hunger worldwide (UN, 2015).

In past few years, many multinational companies attempted to address social issues like food and nutrition through their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). CSR demonstrates the relationship between multinational organizations, government of countries they operate in and citizens. In other words, CSR is a correlation between organizations and stakeholders (Crowther, 2008). Regardless the industry, almost every corporation today tends to be socially responsible towards environment they operate.

The Marriot Hotel invests in communities through their foundation, “Spirit to Serve Our Communities.” Their CSR emphasizes on five prominent areas namely Shelter and Food, Environment, Ready for Jobs, Vitality of Children and Empowering Diversity. Regarding shelter and food, the organization gives corporate donations and conduct fundraising programs to disaster victims by collaborating with International Federation of Red Cross. Marriot Hotel offers millions of points of hotel stays and cash incentives to charitable organizations globally (Marriot, 2015).

Correspondingly, Starwood Hotels and Resorts address community development through financial contributions. In 2013, the company donated \$5.1 millions in charity and raised further \$1 million for Starwood Associate Relief Fund in the same year. This organization utilizes

resources in respect to strategies allowing them to implement Global Citizenship for society welfare (Starwood, 2015).

Conclusion

Henceforth, with engagement of innumerable multinational corporations worldwide there are many social issues elevated in past few decades. Globalization did bring many national enhancements in countries yet deteriorated the social picture simultaneously. However, with the sustainability factor in consideration, organizations are comparatively more responsible towards society and relating issues. Companies consider CSR as a productive obligation and tend to improve it with time. Names like Marriot Hotels are determined to develop communities with their social campaigns and organizational activities.

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